

Key Performance Indicators to be monitored (clinical management)

WP1 Y1Q4

Task leader: Hospital Universitario de Getafe

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INDEX

1	Introduction.....	5
2	From the general evaluation framework to the patient's safety KPIs.....	7
2.1	An overall framework	7
2.2	Logic model to define KPIs	9
2.1	Measurement ideas on the patient's perspective.....	11
2.2	Possible patient's safety KPIs.....	17
2.3	Validation and selection of patient's safety KPIs.....	32
3	First set of KPIs to monitor the DECI pilots.....	37
4	Conclusions	43
5	References	44
6	Appendix A: KPI template.....	45

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Executive Summary

This document focuses on determining Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that will be used as measurable values that demonstrate (or refute) how effectively DECI project is achieving its key business objectives.

More specifically, KPIs to be proposed will be those outcomes focused on patient safety, given the fact that this issue is of major importance in MCI and mild dementia care. Patient harm can occur as a result of the combination of several causes and circumstances and understanding the magnitude of the problem and the main contributing factors that lead to patient harm is essential to devise effective and efficient solutions for the different contexts and environments.

In this document, it will be also presented an initial approach to the whole project evaluation framework and a first set of KPIs to be extended within WP6.

1 Introduction

This document is the outcome of task *T 1.4: Identification of key indicators for performance evaluation on the side of clinical management*. Task 1.4 is part of *WP 1: Analysis of existing models for managing elderly people with cognitive impairment and of their needs*. Task 1.4 focuses on **patient safety evaluation, analysing and defining relevant risks, avoid hazards, preventing emergency calls**, etc. The identification of KPIs right from the first stages of the project will allow a constant and durable monitoring of results throughout the entire initiative: **short term goals and long term objectives** will help tracing the overall activity progress and planning underway measures whenever needed.

An ideal indicator is based on agreed definitions and described exhaustively and exclusively. It has the following characteristics:

- Is highly or optimally specific and sensitive, i.e. detecting few false positives and false negatives;
- Is valid and reliable;
- Discriminates well;
- Relates to clearly identifiable events for the user (e.g. if meant for clinical providers, it is relevant to clinical practice);
- Permits useful comparisons;
- Is evidence-based.

This task is strictly related with other tasks of WP1, especially the T1.3 which specified the needs and requirements and, in general, declined them among a set of specific clusters: patient support elements and caregivers support elements. It is therefore important to analyse and identify all relevant needs that will subsequently be validated during solution design activities in order to develop the most significant components of the resulting model. This task has delivered two documents: D1.3 and D1.5. D1.3: *Patients, caregivers and support and clinical organisational needs* focused on the most relevant needs and characteristics of older adults affected by Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI) and Mild Dementia (MD) and will help tracing all the most significant requirements that will have to be taken into consideration during development and pilot projects of the overall initiative. On the other hand, D1.5: *Design of the final pilot based on the pre pilot study* that has identified the final number of patients, variables and services to test the services in older adults with MCI or MD. T1.4 defined KPIs from a patient security perspective starting from the needs and the related DECI scenarios emerged within T1.3.

As regards the use of D1.4 results in following activities of the DECI project, the WPs with major impact are WP5 and WP6.

The aim of WP5 is the actual experimentation of business models, processes and ICT tools in the pilot settings. Specific variables to be measured in each pilot site will be defined within the testing protocol and derived from the KPIs identified in WP1 and WP6.

WP6 aims at evaluating the business, industrial and quality impacts of the DECI initiative in the four pilot sites. Task 6.1 defines the assessment to be performed, the relevant performances to be monitored, such as patient value, health, process effectiveness, clinical outcome, patient empowerment, patient and professional satisfaction, patient

quality of life, etc.; this task also defines a set of measurable KPIs indicators for each evaluation area. This task will feed D6.1, but first results of these activities are reported in the present deliverable in order to give an **overall view of the general evaluation framework applied to measure the benefits of the design Business Models applied within the project.**

Finally, we reported a **first set of KPIs**, including the patient's safety indicators, **to monitor the DECI pilots**, to be integrated within WP6 when the pilot settings are defined.

2 From the general evaluation framework to the patient's safety KPIs

2.1 An overall framework

Within the Work Package 6, DECI results will be assessed with regards to the quality of care, patient value and organizational impact. To perform the assessment, the evaluation framework outlining the methodology for evaluation will be developed as a result of the task 6.1. The evaluation methodology will incorporate both qualitative and quantitative methods to track the critical measures that will help to verify DECI concept and to determine its transferability. The assessment will focus on the following areas:

- Health outcomes;
- Patients' safety;
- Patients' empowerment;
- Patients' satisfaction;
- Caregiver's satisfaction
- Usage of the system by the patients;
- Adherence and compliance of patients to treatment;
- Patient's quality of life;
- Process effectiveness;
- Healthcare professionals' satisfaction;
- Costs.

Since the methodology of evaluation is under development stage, D.1.4 focused on one of the key focus areas: patient safety. Deliverable 1.4 incorporates the elaborated set of KPIs that will help to determine the incidents and perceptions to safety. KPIs for other areas of assessment that are outlined above, have been decided to develop after the local pilot designs are finalized. Over the Year 1, the general principles of evaluation with preliminary sets of KPIs have been defined.

The guiding principles to the evaluation have been determined within the consortium to inform the design of the framework. The evaluation framework will incorporate a reasonable amount of KPIs with a careful consideration to the time and human resources that measurement of those KPIs will demand. Further, the aim will be to develop a set of KPIs that will be targeted to the goals of DECI and that can help to understand to what extent they have been achieved. A flexible approach will be applied to the measurement process, meaning that the evaluation framework might be reconsidered and adjusted if sufficient amount of reasonable argumentation is collected on why some parts of the framework should be changed.

KPIs will be determined in four major categories: patient, staff, organization and cost. A general set of KPIs will be developed within task 6.1 and then localized depending on the pilot design in each site.

Table 1 shows a few examples outlining preliminary areas of the general set of KPIs are presented.

Patient/ family	<p>The KPI area of “Patient” will aim to assess the health outcomes and experiences as service users while using the ICT of DECI.</p> <p>Preliminary KPI areas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health outcomes. • Communication with primary care doctors and nurses. • Patient’s safety. • Patient’s satisfaction. • Patient’s empowerment • Waiting times to service. • Frequency of certain critical events. • Experience of the DECI technology used. • Relatives experience and satisfaction. • Family’s satisfaction.
Staff	<p>The KPI area of “Staff” will aim to assess the perceptions of involved health and social care staff over the DECI concept and pilots itself, and changes to their daily routines.</p> <p>Preliminary KPI areas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal experience of the piloted activity (changes to role, activities and work practices). • Views about health and social care quality received by patients. • Communication within and between participating organisations. • Communication with other health and social care staff. • Professionals’ satisfaction.
Organization	<p>In analyzing data on “Organization” area of evaluation, the principal focus will be placed on tracking changes in local care processes and hospitalization rates.</p> <p>Preliminary KPI areas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emergency admissions. • Length of hospital stays. • Number of reported incidents when DECI technology was not available to use. • Experienced benefits and drawbacks of implementing the technology.
Costs	<p>The KPIs area of cost aims identifying categories of cost incurred and to estimate the scale of resources required for each category in each</p>

	<p>site. Additionally, it is important to understand how much the approach might cost if it was implemented elsewhere.</p> <p>Preliminary KPI areas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Costs of service. • Fixed costs. • Additional running costs to keep the project resourced. • Overall investment costs.
System	<p>The KPIs area of system aims at evaluating the DECI system implemented within the project. Please, notice that this KPIs area is cross to the previous ones. Following, some KPIs examples of this area:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Usage of the system by the patients. • Adoption of technologies in the pilot sites. • Adherence of the DECI solution to pilots' needs.

Table 1 Preliminary areas of KPIs

KPIs, within WP6, will be detailed and linked to the various phases of the care process for patients with MCI/MD (1), analysed within Task 3.2:

- Noticing symptoms and first detection;
- Assessment and diagnosis;
- Treatment and care service definition;
- Service delivery and follow-up.

One of the links between the phases of the care process and the KPIs is related to the multitude of technologies that will be adopted in the four pilot sites and the related functionalities (analysed within Task 2.1 and clustered in Task 3.1). Each class/cluster of functionalities can have an impact on one or more phases of the care process and this impact will be assessed through the KPIs that, as stated before, are developed within Task 6.1.

2.2 Logic model to define KPIs

It is important to define the goals of the measurement, reasons for measurement and the intended audience in order to identify and develop a suitable KPI centred in patient safety. The audience refers to the person or group for whom the KPI will aid decision-making and can be the service-user, the clinician, the public, the facility or the healthcare system. A useful tool to help conceptualize the production process of KPIs is the 'logic model'. In strategic planning, logic models are used commonly to describe logical linkages between problems and their solutions; Figure 1 depicts the proposed logic model.

Figure 1 Logic model

The three stages of the model are described next:

1. Identifying the problem(s) and need(s). The needs and requirements of patients, caregivers and organizations are described in Deliverable 1.3.
2. Developing policies or measures to address the problem(s). Solutions that aim to bridge the gaps in the health care process of people with MCI and MD are presented.
3. Articulating the desired goals – the end-state of affairs or vision for the future.

This model is applied in the following sections to patients perspective and then to patient's safety.

2.1 Measurement ideas on the patient's perspective

The main reason for monitoring health and social care quality is to identify opportunities to improve performance where it has been highlighted that performance is not at the desired standard.

Outcome KPIs are intended to transform research questions into measurable indicators. Important; these indicators should be standardised, with uniform definitions, to ensure that they are collected consistently, supporting measurement process and facilitating meaningful comparisons. For KPIs to be effective, they need to have clear definitions to ensure that the data collected is of high quality (that is, consisting, reliable and in keeping with shared definitions).

In the studied scenario, outcome KPIs must consider all the effects of healthcare on patients and populations, including changes to health status, behaviour or knowledge as well as patient satisfaction and health-related quality of life. Outcomes are sometimes seen as the most important indicators of quality because improving patient health status is the goal of healthcare.

The importance of patient and family engagement is well documented in dementia process indicators; however, there remains a notable absence of indicators addressing such engagement-related outcomes. The DWG (Dementia measures Work Group) in the US proposed several outcomes related to the concept of engagement for future consideration, such as promoting caregiver and patient-centred decision making, reducing caregiver stress and burden, improving quality of life, and enhancing caregiver involvement and comfort with dementia care(2).

This section will provide a framework for analysing how DECI will measure that the intervention is helping reaching the stakeholder's goals (Table 1) on the patient's perspective.

Goals	1 st service encounters	Assessment and diagnosis	Care service definition		Service delivery and maintenance
			MCI	MD	
To maintain or improve the functional status of people with MCI or MD.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evaluation of functional status 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IADL ADL <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Frailty Nutrition 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Encourage a healthy life style including exercise 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Encourage a Healthy life style including exercises 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IADL ADL Frailty MNA(Mininutritional Assessment) Exercise program, with feedback and motivational messages
To improve the quality of life of people with MCI or MD and their caregivers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Awareness about the disease. Information about the disease. Caregiver or family member as part of the intervention 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Psychosocial factors Behavioural Functional status(independence) Pain control 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Address the behaviour that challenges Assess Depression 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Address the behaviour that challenges Assess Depression 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Questionnaire tool(EuroQL, Caregiver burden, Wellbeing, NPI, GDS) Support groups online Information and feedback of clinical professionals

<p>To improve or maintain the cognitive level of patients</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early identification of dementia • Encourage a Healthy life style (exercise, stop smoking ,alcohol moderation, diabetes control, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment of cognition • Delay in cognitive decline • 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitoring cognitive function in time of cognition • Assess Depression • Referral to specialists to manage medical conditions with effect on cognition • Delay in cognitive decline • Encourage healthy lifestyle • Cognitive stimulation program 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitoring cognitive function in time • Assess Depression • Referral to specialists to manage medical conditions with effect on cognition • Delay in cognitive decline • Encourage healthy life style(CV risk, exercise) • Cognitive stimulation program 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MMSE or Moca • Clock drawing test • Cognitive stimulation and training • Leisure activities (games, chats, reading) • Analysis, scoring and follow up of cognitive performances • Alerts in case of cognitive decline
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<p>Safety</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Falls • Medication • Safe walking • Safe at home • Driving • Home monitoring • Behaviour 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Falls • Medication • Safe walking • Safe at home • Driving • Home monitoring 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Avoid anticholinergic medication • Patients Falls • Possible undetected pain or discomfort 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Side effects of antipsychotic drugs or cholinergic • Avoid anticholinergic drugs • Patient Falls • GPS for safe walking(wandering) or emergency call 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information about the dementia medication side effects and the possibility to ask the case manager • Electronic Trigger Tool-surveillance (anticholinergic drugs) • Protocols for dementia care • Emergency calls or admission • Comprehensive and coordinated treatment plan including medication and physical activity with reminders and alerts
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<p>Patient centeredness</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Privacy • Individual biography, including religious beliefs and spiritual and cultural identity • Educate the individual and family regarding the illness, available treatments and interventions. • Support families to continue home care with dignity and quality of life. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Privacy • Individual biography, including religious beliefs and spiritual and cultural identity • Educate the individual and family regarding the illness, available treatments and interventions 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to relevant information on the platform regarding the illness, available treatments, legal aspects etc. • Ability to contact health professionals directly
<p>Effectiveness</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduce premature nursing home placements, reducing health care costs. • Reduce emergency calls • Adherence to the technology service • Easy to use 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy PC and smartphone access from the comfort of home and suitable for everyday use

Table 2 Measurement ideas on the patient's perspective

In the next paragraphs, we focus on the analysis of patients' safety KPIs, defined within Task 1.4.

2.2 Possible patient's safety KPIs

Patient safety is an essential issue in dementia care. Patient harm can occur as a result of a constellation of factors and circumstances. Understanding the magnitude of the problem and the main contributing factors that lead to patient harm is of major importance to devise effective and efficient solutions for the different contexts and environments. The growing sophistication of computers and software should allow technology to play a vital part in reducing patient risk by streamlining care, catching and correction errors, assisting with decisions, and providing feedback performance.

Dementia makes aspects of day-to-day life more difficult for the person living with the condition. In some cases, it may also put the subject at risk; for instance, in the home environment, things like repeatedly mislaying keys can be frustrating, while other events like leaving the gas unlit can be very dangerous.

DECI project proposes both cognitive stimulation and assistive technologies¹ to help patients to cope with their daily-living activities. The use of DECI technology can be useful to prevent risks and adverse events, but it is very important to highlight that it can never replace human contact and interaction and it should never be used for this purpose; doing so may lead to feelings of isolation and loneliness for the person with MCI or dementia. It also imperative to be aware that assistive technology will not eliminate risk; it can only assist people in improving their safety and wellbeing, not in providing perfect solutions. DECI technology (i.e. telecare or remote monitoring) is focused on increasing safety and reducing risk.

Some related products may not have been initially designed taking into account the specific wants of the target population (people suffering from MCI or dementia) in mind so it is expected and demanded that they adapt to technology and not the opposite. Expecting the impaired persons to adapt to technology, without listening to their needs can affect how keen they are to use the technology. In the DECI project we adapt the technological systems to the needs of the person with MCI or dementia and the care network:

- **Integration system**, a platform that integrates all patient's data that can be used by socio-healthcare professional to share information;
- **Activity and monitoring system**, a wearable device that monitors patient's activities in terms of movements (e.g. falls);
- **Coaching and training system**, a web tool that support the patient's in daily activities, through reminder and training courses.

¹ Assistive technology refers to devices or systems that support a person to maintain or improve their independence, safety and wellbeing. It tends to refer to devices and systems that assist people with memory problems or other cognitive difficulties (12)

Considering the DECI solution, we have designed 17 patient's safety KPIs to be evaluated with clinical partners for a later selection of the most important ones. Please, notice that we are considering KPIs not only strictly directed to safety (e.g. adherence to physical activity) since improving patients' status is also related with their safety.

Each possible KPI is described following the template presented in Appendix A in the next tables.

KPI Title	Falls reporting
KPI Identifier	KPI 001
KPI Description	Falls are defined as an event which results in a person coming to rest inadvertently on the ground or floor or other lower level (3)
KPI Target	To identify the number of falls suffered by a MCI or dementia patient
Expected result	We DO NOT expect to observe a reduction in the number of falls suffered by the patients within the project scope, but we will check that: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Falls are appropriately reported • Alarms regarding falls are generated • Trends can be observed
KPI calculation	Number of falls/time
Data Source(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activity monitor • Questionnaire
Data collection frequency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activity monitor: continuous • Questionnaire: pre and post intervention
Temporality	Long term
Related need category	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient needs: mobility/falls • Professional needs: health care provision
Applicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • na-MCI • a-MCI • MD

Table 3 KPI 001

KPI Title	Safe walking
KPI Identifier	KPI 002
KPI Description	Safe physical walking means that a person walks independently with the help of technology (e.g. alarm system, tracking devices or location monitoring services) to have a greater freedom and can ultimately reduce the use of unpleasant solutions such as drugs and physical restraint(4,5).
KPI Target	To register the wandering behavior of a MCI or dementia patient

Expected result	<p>We DO NOT expect to observe a reduction in the number of walks out of the 'safe' area within the project scope, but:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Professionals are fed with reliable information regarding if a patient wanders around • Caregivers know when the patient leaves the 'safe' area (anxiety reduction) • Trends can be observed
KPI calculation	Number of walks out of the 'safe' area/time
Data Source(s)	Activity monitor
Data collection frequency	Continuous
Temporality	Short term
Related need category	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient needs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Behavior ○ inadvertent self-harm • Caregiver needs: anxiety • Professional needs: health care provision
Applicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • na-MCI • a-MCI • MD

Table 4 KPI 002

KPI Title	Life space
KPI Identifier	KPI 003
KPI Description	Finding out how much the person gets out and about and the spatial extent of the person's typical life space (i.e. what is the usual range of places in which the person engages in activities within the designated time frame) (7)
KPI Target	To register the variation of the life space amplitude of a MCI or dementia patient
Expected result	<p>We DO NOT expect to observe general changes in the life spaces of the patients within the project scope, but:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Professionals are fed with reliable information regarding the broadening or shrinking of a patient life space • Trends can be observed

KPI calculation	The difference between the life space amplitude at the beginning and at the end of a period of time
Data Source(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activity monitor • Questionnaire
Data collection frequency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activity monitor: continuous • Questionnaire: pre and post intervention
Temporality	Long term
Related need category	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient needs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ mobility/falls ○ psychological distress • Professional needs: health care provision
Applicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • na-MCI • a-MCI • MD

Table 5 KPI 003

KPI Title	Under the counter drugs
KPI Identifier	KPI 004
KPI Description	Under the counter drugs are defined as those medicines sold directly to a consumer without a prescription, from a healthcare professional (8)
KPI Target	To identify if a MCI or dementia patient is increasing or reducing the use of under the counter drugs.
Expected result	We DO NOT expect to observe a general reduction in the use of under the counter drug intake, but: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Professionals can identify cognitive/functional decline risk factors related to non-prescribed drug intake • To check if there is communication among the involved actors (caregivers, health care professionals)
KPI calculation	The number of under the counter pills taken by a MCI or dementia patient in a period of time.
Data Source(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Questionnaire • Integrated care platform
Data collection frequency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Questionnaire: pre and post intervention • Integrated care platform: daily/weekly
Temporality	Short term
Related need category	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient needs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Drugs ○ deliberate self-harm ○ inadvertent self-harm • Professional needs: health care provision
Applicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • na-MCI • a-MCI • MD

Table 6 KPI 004

KPI Title	Non-appropriate emergency calls
KPI Identifier	KPI 005
KPI Description	The number of non-appropriate emergency calls performed by the patient during the pilot
KPI Target	To identify how the MCI or dementia patient is using the emergency call service

Expected result	<p>We DO NOT expect to observe a significant reduction in the number of non-appropriate emergency calls due to the influence of the integrated care platform, but we will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quantify the number of appropriate and non-appropriate emergency calls • Know if there is communication between the involved stakeholders
KPI calculation	Number of voluntary emergency calls in a period of time
Data Source(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrated care platform • Questionnaire
Data collection frequency	Daily
Temporality	Short term
Related need category	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient needs: behavior • Patient needs: psychological distress • Professional needs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ healthcare provision ○ social care
Applicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • na-MCI • a-MCI • MD

Table 7 KPI 005

KPI Title	Driving frequency
KPI Identifier	KPI 006
KPI Description	The definition driving is the ability to drive a car. The driving frequency is how many times the patient drive during the pilot
KPI Target	To know if the patients are driving after being diagnosed
Expected result	<p>We DO NOT expect to observe a significant modification in the patients' conduct related to driving within the project scope, but:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To observe if the patients have a better understanding of their condition (behavior modification) • Empowerment of the caregivers •

KPI calculation	Asking the patients and caregivers if they are driving.
Data Source(s)	Questionnaires
Data collection frequency	Pre and post intervention
Temporality	Short term
Related need category	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient needs: information on condition and treatment • Caregiver needs: anxiety
Applicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • na-MCI • a-MCI • MD

Table 8 KPI 006

KPI Title	Neuropsychiatric inventory (NPI): patient
KPI Identifier	KPI 007
KPI Description	<p>The NPI (7) is a screening test administered to a caregiver that evaluates behavioral domains with positive responses to screening questions. Frequency and the severity of each behavior are determined.</p> <p>Behaviours: hallucinations, delusions, agitation/aggression, dysphoria/depression, anxiety, irritability, disinhibition, euphoria, apathy, aberrant motor behavior, sleep and night-time behavior change, appetite and eating change.</p>
KPI Target	To evaluate the neuropsychiatric status of the MCI or dementia patient
Expected result	<p>We DO NOT expect to observe a significant improvement of the patients in terms of NPI within the project scope, but:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To know the evolution of the patients in terms of NPI • Trends can be observed
KPI calculation	Application of the NPI
Data Source(s)	Questionnaires (can be delivered in the integrated care platform)
Data collection frequency	Pre and post intervention

Temporality	Long term
Related need category	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Professional needs: healthcare provision
Applicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> na-MCI a-MCI MD

Table 9 KPI 007

KPI Title	NPI: caregiver/family
KPI Identifier	KPI 008
KPI Description	NPI items related to caregiver distress are based on the following question: 'how emotionally distressing do you find this behavior?'
KPI Target	To evaluate the neuropsychiatric status pf the caregiver
Expected result	<p>We DO NOT expect to observe a significant improvement of the caregivers in terms of NPI within the project scope, but we will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Know the evolution of the caregivers in terms of NPI Observe trends
KPI calculation	Application of the NPI
Data Source(s)	Questionnaires (can be delivered in the integrated care platform)
Data collection frequency	Pre and post intervention
Temporality	Long term
Related need category	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Professional needs: healthcare provision
Applicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> na-MCI a-MCI MD

Table 10 KPI 008

KPI Title	Minimum dataset
KPI Identifier	KPI 009
KPI Description	In DECI project the minimum data set (8) is defined as the clinical measurements (MMSE, Clock

	drawing test, Clinical Dementia Rating Scale, Basic ADL, Instrumental ADL, Camberwell Assessment for the Elderly Short form (CANE-S)
KPI Target	To evaluate the measurements included in the minimum data set
Expected result	We DO NOT expect to observe a significant improvement of the patients in terms of MDS within the project scope, but we will: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Know the evolution of the patients in terms of the minimum dataset • Observe trends
KPI calculation	Application of the different test or scales
Data Source(s)	Questionnaires (can be delivered in the integrated care platform) or other data source according to pilot site data (such as EHR)
Data collection frequency	Pre and post intervention
Temporality	Long term
Related need category	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Professional needs: healthcare provision
Applicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • na-MCI • a-MCI • MD

Table 11 KPI 009

KPI Title	Hospital admissions
KPI Identifier	KPI 010
KPI Description	Staying at a hospital for at least one night
KPI Target	To know if a MCI or dementia patient is being admitted very often in a hospital
Expected result	We DO NOT expect to observe a significant reduction in the number of hospital admissions due to the influence of the integrated care platform, but we will: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quantify the number of hospital admissions • Know if there is communication between the involved stakeholders
KPI calculation	Asking the patients and caregivers for information and automatically registering admissions
Data Source(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Questionnaires • Integrated care platform

Data collection frequency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Questionnaire: pre and post intervention • Integrated care platform: continuous
Temporality	Short term
Related need category	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Professional needs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ healthcare provision ○ social care
Applicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • na-MCI • a-MCI • MD

Table 12 KPI 010

KPI Title	Primary care visits
KPI Identifier	KPI 011
KPI Description	Primary care is a health care provided by a medical professional (as a general practitioner, or nurse) with whom a patient has a close contact with the patient
KPI Target	To know how often a MCI or dementia patient visits a primary care centre
Expected result	<p>We DO NOT expect to observe a significant reduction in the number of primary care visits due to the influence of the integrated care platform, but we will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quantify the number of primary care visits • Know if there is communication between the involved stakeholders
KPI calculation	Asking the patients and caregivers for information and automatically registering visits
Data Source(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Questionnaire • Integrated care platform
Data collection frequency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Questionnaires: pre and post intervention • Integrated care platform: continuous
Temporality	Short term
Related need category	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Professional needs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ healthcare provision ○ social care
Applicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • na-MCI • a-MCI • MD

Table 13 KPI 011

KPI Title	Emergency visits
KPI Identifier	KPI 012
KPI Description	Every time that a patient visits the Emergency Department
KPI Target	To know how often a MCI or dementia patient uses the emergency service at the hospital.
Expected result	We DO NOT expect to observe a significant reduction in the number of emergency care visits due to the influence of the integrated care platform, but we will: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quantify the number of primary emergency visits • Know if there is communication between the involved stakeholders
KPI calculation	Asking the patients and caregivers for information and automatically registering visits
Data Source(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Questionnaires • Integrated care platform
Data collection frequency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Questionnaire: pre and post intervention • Integrated care platform: continuous
Temporality	Short term
Related need category	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Professional needs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ healthcare provision ○ social care
Applicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • na-MCI • a-MCI • MD

Table 14 KPI 012

KPI Title	Adherence to cognitive stimulation
KPI Identifier	KPI 013
KPI Description	Cognitive stimulation (10) is an intervention for people with MCI and dementia which offers a range of enjoyable activities providing general stimulation for thinking, concentration and memory. The adherence is the obedience of the patient to the medical advice of the cognitive stimulation with the use of DECI technology

KPI Target	To know if a patient follows the prescribed cognitive stimulation training
Expected result	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Professionals are fed with reliable information regarding the adherence to treatments • Trends can be observed
KPI calculation	The number of executions/ number of prescribed exercises
Data Source(s)	Integrated care platform
Data collection frequency	Daily/weekly (according to treatment plan)
Temporality	Short term
Related need category	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient needs: daytime activities • Professional needs: healthcare provision
Applicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • na-MCI • a-MCI • MD

Table 15 KPI 013

KPI Title	Adherence to physical activity
KPI Identifier	KPI 014
KPI Description	Physical activity (11) is any body movement that works the muscles, requiring more energy than resting. The adherence is the obedience of the patient to medical advice of the physical activity prescribed with DECI
KPI Target	To know if a patient follows the prescribed physical activity
Expected result	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Professionals are fed with reliable information regarding the adherence to treatments • Trends can be observed
KPI calculation	The number of executions/ number of prescribed exercises
Data Source(s)	Integrated care platform
Data collection frequency	Daily
Temporality	Short term

Related need category	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient needs: daytime activities • Professional needs: healthcare provision
Applicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • na-MCI • a-MCI • MD

Table 16 KPI 014

KPI Title	Adherence to the prescribed anti-dementia medication
KPI Identifier	KPI 015
KPI Description	Refers to whether a patient takes his/her medications as prescribed (6)
KPI Target	To know if a patient follows the prescribed medication
Expected result	<p>We DO NOT expect to observe a significant increase in the adherence to the prescribed medication, but:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Professionals are fed with reliable information regarding the adherence to treatments • Trends can be observed
KPI calculation	Asking the patients and caregivers for information
Data Source(s)	Questionnaires
Data collection frequency	Pre and post intervention
Temporality	Short term
Related need category	Professional needs: healthcare provision
Applicability	MD

Table 17 KPI 015

KPI Title	Cognitive evolution
KPI Identifier	KPI 016
KPI Description	Refers to how a patient has evolved in his/her prescribed cognitive stimulation
KPI Target	To know if a patient is improving from a cognitive perspective
Expected result	We DO NOT expect to observe a significant improvement of patients' evolution related to the cognitive stimulation tasks, but:

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To know the cognitive evolution of the patients related to the cognitive training Trends can be observed
KPI calculation	Obtained results in the cognitive stimulation tasks
Data Source(s)	Integrated care platform
Data collection frequency	Daily/weekly (according to treatment plan)
Temporality	Short term
Related need category	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Professional needs: healthcare provision
Applicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> na-MCI a-MCI MD

Table 18 KPI 016

KPI Title	Physical evolution
KPI Identifier	KPI 017
KPI Description	Refers to how a patient has evolved in his/her prescribed physical activity
KPI Target	To know if a patient is improving from a physical perspective
Expected result	<p>We DO NOT expect to observe a significant improvement of patients' evolution related to the physical training tasks, but:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> To know the cognitive evolution of the patients related to the physical training Trends can be observed
KPI calculation	Obtained results in the physical tasks
Data Source(s)	Integrated care platform
Data collection frequency	Daily
Temporality	Short term
Related need category	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Professional needs: healthcare provision
Applicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> na-MCI a-MCI MD

Table 19 KPI 017

2.3 Validation and selection of patient's safety KPIs

To validate and select the patient's safety KPIs, we applied a Delphi technique. This is a facilitated structured process, whereby a panel of experts complete questionnaires and, through feedback and scoring over a number of rounds where some elements are discarded, a consensus is achieved on a final set. In our application of this technique, the "elements" are the "KPIs".

The KPIs are validated with the clinical partners. Glossary:

- **Validity:** does the KPI measure what is supposed to measure? Ideally, selected KPIs should have links to processes and outcomes through scientific evidence.
- **Reliability:** does the KPI provide a consistent measure?
- **Feasibility:** is it possible to collect the required data and is it worth the resources?
- **Relevance:** what useful decisions can be made from the KPI?

Each KPI will be validated by using the scoring matrix presented in Table 20.

Validity	The KPI measures a specific variable susceptible to be measured	1-3 Strong disagreement 4-6 Medium agreement 7-10 High degree of agreement
Reliability	The KPI is independent of who or what performs the measurement	1-3 Strong disagreement 4-6 Medium agreement 7-10 High degree of agreement
Feasibility	Data source to obtain the KPI is continuously available	1-3 Strong disagreement 4-6 Medium agreement 7-10 High degree of agreement
Relevance	Relevant conclusions can be obtained from the KPI	1-3 Strong disagreement 4-6 Medium agreement 7-10 High degree of agreement

Table 20 Assessment instrument

FDG (Italy), VDG (Sweden), MAC (Israel) and HUG (Spain) validated the proposed KPIs. Table 21 depicts the obtained scores. In Table 22 KPIs are ranked according to the average score.

		KPI 001	KPI 002	KPI 003	KPI 004	KPI 005	KPI 006	KPI 007	KPI 009	KPI 009	KPI 010	KPI 011	KPI 012	KPI 013	KPI 014	KPI 015	KPI 016	KPI 017
FDG	Validity	9	8	8	8	9	7	8	8	8	9	9	9	9	9	8	9	7
	Reliability	8	9	7	5	9	5	5	5	5	7	7	8	8	8	3	6	4
	Feasibility	6	9	8	5	9	4	3	3	3	8	8	8	8	8	3	5	5
	Relevance	7	4	7	6	6	4	8	9	9	8	7	8	7	7	5	8	7
HUG	Validity	9	8	8	9	9	9	9	9	10	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9
	Reliability	7	9	9	6	10	6	6	6	7	7	7	6	8	9	4	7	7
	Feasibility	8	8	8	6	9	5	5	5	6	9	9	9	10	10	4	9	9
	Relevance	9	7	8	7	7	8	8	9	9	7	6	9	8	8	8	8	9
VGR	Validity	9	8	8	5	9	5	8	8	8	9	9	9	9	9	8	9	7
	Reliability	9	7	8	4	9	4	5	6	6	9	8	8	8	8	3	6	5
	Feasibility	6	5	8	3	9	3	4	3	5	8	8	8	8	8	3	6	5
	Relevance	8	4	7	7	7	3	8	8	9	8	7	8	7	7	7	7	9
MAC	Validity	9	8	7	5	9	8	8	8	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9
	Reliability	9	7	4	3	8	6	6	6	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	9
	Feasibility	8	6	5	4	4	6	5	5	7	4	8	4	8	8	8	8	8
	Relevance	7	3	7	8	6	3	8	8	9	4	9	4	9	7	6	9	7

Table 21 Validation results

Rank	KPI identifier	Average score
1	013	8.31
2	014	8.25
3	005	8.06
4	001	8
5	011	8
6	016	7.87
7	012	7.75
8	010	7.68
9	009	7.37
10	003	7.31
11	017	7.12
12	002	6.87
13	008	6.6
14	007	6.5
15	015	6
16	004	5.68
17	006	5.37

Table 22 Ranked KPIs

Based on this evaluation, the best evaluated KPI (first one in the ranking) is KPI 013 (adherence to cognitive stimulation). Also KPIs 014 (adherence to physical activity), 005 (voluntary emergency calls), 001 (falls reporting) and 011 (primary care visits) received an overall score equal or higher than 8. The KPI with the worst ranking is KPI 006 (driving frequency).

But if only relevance is taken into account, the most valuable KPI is 010 (minimum dataset), with an average score of 9. This fact makes a lot of sense since it is related to the screening tests that evaluate the evolution of the target patients; the main problem associated to the measurement of this KPI is its feasibility, due to the inherent subjectivity of the application of the scales. In terms of relevance, KPIs 017 (cognitive evolution), 009 (NPI: caregiver/family) and 008 (NPI: patient) also have received a high averaged score (8 or higher).

After the validation process, six patient safety related KPIs have been selected according to the obtained scores and relevance (the five best scored and the one with the highest relevance). These KPIs will be included in the DECI evaluation framework. These KPIs are:

- KPI 001: Falls reporting
- KPI 005: Non-appropriate emergency calls
- KPI 009: Minimum dataset²
- KPI 011: Primary care visits
- KPI 013: Adherence to cognitive stimulation
- KPI 014: Adherence to physical activity

² This KPI has been included due to its obtained high relevance score

3 First set of KPIs to monitor the DECI pilots

This Chapter reports a first set of KPIs that we are going to measure within the project to monitor the pilots' results.

Starting from the macro-categories of evaluation define within the overall framework described in the Chapter 2, we describe a set of KPIs that we are going to measure, including the patient's safety KPIs defined in the previous chapters. We have selected this first set of KPIs also basing on the MAFEIP framework³, which describes the main areas to be monitored on EIP initiatives on Active and Healthy Ageing as the DECI project.

The identified KPIs for each area are the following:

- Patient/caregiver:
 - Safety:
 - KPI 001: Falls reporting;
 - KPI 005: Non-appropriate emergency calls;
 - KPI 009: Minimum dataset;
 - KPI 011: Primary care visits;
 - KPI 013: Adherence to cognitive stimulation;
 - KPI 014: Adherence to physical activity;
 - Satisfaction:
 - KPI 018 Usability satisfaction;
 - KPI 019 Burden of the caregiver;
- Organization:
 - KPI 020: Multidisciplinary team meeting/consultancy;
- Staff:
 - KPI 021 Professionals' satisfaction using the DECI solution;
- Cost:
 - KPI 022: Cost of the home care service.

In the following tables we describe the KPIs that are not related to patients' safety, following the general schema reported in Appendix A:

KPI Title	Usability satisfaction
KPI Identifier	KPI 018
KPI Description	Patients affected by MCI/MD could have some problems in using technology, for this reason is fundamental to monitor the usability satisfaction on the patient's perspective

³ Monitoring and Assessment Framework for the European Innovation Partnership on Active and Healthy Ageing: http://ec.europa.eu/research/innovation-union/index_en.cfm?section=active-healthy-ageing&pg=mafeip.

KPI Target	Monitor the usability satisfaction of patients/caregivers
Expected result	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Level of satisfaction no lower than 6 out of 10 (at the 6th month of the pilot) • Level of satisfaction no lower than 8 out of (at the end of the pilot)
Related need category	Patient's needs (cross)
KPI calculation	Average usability satisfaction of patient in the DECI group
Data Source(s)	Questionnaires
Data collection frequency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At the 6th month of the pilot • At the end of the pilot
Temporality	Medium term
Applicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • na-MCI • a-MCI • MD

Table 23 KPI 018

KPI Title	Burden of the caregiver
KPI Identifier	KPI 019
KPI Description	Caregiver burden is the stress perceived by caregivers due to the home care situation
KPI Target	Monitor the burden of the caregiver
Expected result	Reduction of the burden of the caregiver, enabled by the DECI Business Model
Related need category	<p>Diagnosis and assessment: caregiver burden</p> <p>Caregivers needs: physical and psychological monitoring of the caregiver</p>
KPI calculation	Average results of Caregiver Burden Inventory (CBI)
Data Source(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Questionnaires (control group) • Integration system (DECI group)
Data collection frequency	Half yearly/ Yearly
Temporality	Medium term

Applicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • na-MCI • a-MCI • MD (more relevant)
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Table 24 KPI 019

KPI Title	Multidisciplinary team meeting/consultancy
KPI Identifier	KPI 020
KPI Description	Efficient and effective multidisciplinary meetings are fundamental for older patients affected by MCI/MD, because of the complexity of the disease and the related comorbidities
KPI Target	Prove that the DECI Business Model enables multidisciplinary team meeting/consultancy
Expected result	Reduction of the duration of multidisciplinary meeting, because home care actors are already aligned and have all data needed to make decisions on the patient
Related need category	Organizational needs Clinical team needs: coordinated care and sharing information Social team needs: coordinated care and sharing information
KPI calculation	Average duration of multidisciplinary meetings/consultancy
Data Source(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Questionnaires (control group, DECI group) • Integration system (DECI group)
Data collection frequency	Monthly
Temporality	Medium term
Applicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • na-MCI • a-MCI • MD

Table 25 KPI 020

KPI Title	Professionals' satisfaction using the DECI solution
KPI Identifier	KPI 021

KPI Description	The DECI solution is dedicated not only to patients but also to healthcare and social care professionals. For this reason it is important to measure their satisfaction
KPI Target	Measure the level satisfaction of home care actors
Expected result	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Level of satisfaction no lower than 6 out of 10 (at the 6th month of the pilot) • Level of satisfaction no lower than 8 out of 10 (at the end of the pilot)
Related need category	<p>Clinical team needs: coordinated care, sharing information, improve diagnosis method</p> <p>Social team needs: coordinated care and sharing information</p>
KPI calculation	Average professionals' satisfaction in the DECI group
Data Source(s)	Questionnaires
Data collection frequency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At the 6th month of the pilot • At the end of the pilot
Temporality	Medium term
Applicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • na-MCI • a-MCI • MD

Table 26 KPI 021

KPI Title	Cost of the home care service
KPI Identifier	KPI 022
KPI Description	The DECI Business Model is aimed at reducing the overall cost of the home care service (both from a patient's perspective and from a professionals' perspective)
KPI Target	Monitoring the difference of home care service costs, both from a patient's perspective and from a professionals' perspective
Expected result	We expect a reduction of the overall home care cost in the long term. For this reason we DO NOT expect a relevant reduction during the pilots
Related need category	Cross needs

KPI calculation	Average cost per patient of the home care service from a patient's perspective and from a professionals' perspective
Data Source(s)	Questionnaires
Data collection frequency	Yearly
Temporality	Long term
Applicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • na-MCI • a-MCI • MD

Table 27 KPI 022

In the following tables, we underline for each KPI of the first set, the DECI solution that impacts on the results of the KPI and the macro-phase of the home care process impacted by the KPI.

	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and maintenance
Integration system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Minimum dataset • Professionals' satisfaction using the DECI solution 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Minimum dataset • Burden of the caregiver • Multidisciplinary team meeting/ consultancy • Professionals' satisfaction using the DECI solution • Cost of the home care service 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adherence to cognitive stimulation • Adherence to physical activity • Burden of the caregiver • Multidisciplinary team meeting/ consultancy • Professionals' satisfaction using the DECI solution • Cost of the home care service 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-appropriate emergency calls • Minimum dataset • Adherence to cognitive stimulation • Adherence to physical activity • Multidisciplinary team meeting/ consultancy • Professionals' satisfaction using the DECI solution • Cost of the home care service

	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and maintenance
Activity and monitoring system				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Falls reporting • Non-appropriate emergency calls • Burden of the caregiver • Usability satisfaction • Professionals' satisfaction using the DECI solution • Cost of the home care service
Coaching and training system				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-appropriate emergency calls • Adherence to cognitive stimulation • Adherence to physical activity • Burden of the caregiver • Usability satisfaction • Professionals' satisfaction using the DECI solution • Cost of the home care service

Table 28 First set of KPIs mapped on macro-phases of the home care process and DECI solutions

4 Conclusions

The definition of KPIs are of major importance since it allows to have an immediate snapshot of the overall performance of a system.

Within the scope of this document, KPIs related to patient safety have been elicited and validated by all DECI clinical partners. After this validation process, KPIs have been ranked in order to have a general idea about the individual importance of each of them, so they can be prioritized when evaluating DECI contributions. Six patient safety related KPIs have been selected starting from this validation.

In Chapter 3 also a first set of general KPIs is described to be included within the first set of KPIs that will be extended and finalized within WP6.

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6 Appendix A: KPI template

KPI Title	Exact title of the KPI
KPI Identifier	Unique identifier of the KPI
KPI Description	Description of the KPI including a description of the target population
KPI Target	Indicate the target for the KPI
Expected result	Indicate the expected result related to the KPI
KPI calculation	Indicate how the KPI will be calculated. This should contain information on the numerator (subset of the target population that meets the criteria as defined in the indicator) and denominator (all services users or events that qualify for inclusion)
Data Source(s)	For example, administrative databases, medical records, national health information resources and or survey data
Data collection frequency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuous • Daily • Weekly • Monthly • Quarterly • ...
Temporality	Time that will take the outcome to be observable: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short term • Medium term • Long term
Related need category	Need category addressed (D1.3 - Patients, caregivers; support and clinical organizational needs)
Applicability	To which patients' cluster the KPI is applicable